

ORIGINAL PAPER

The use of photogrammetry in assessing the stability of escarpment of a ditch draining a forest road

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ABSTRACT

The stability of slopes and ditch bottoms, as elements of the road, is an important factor in keeping the road drainage system operational. This paper presents the practical application of close-range photogrammetry, GIS analysis on rasters, and geotechnical studies to determine the stability of a sample roadside ditch slope over a three-year period from 2019. The studied object is located in the Limanowa Forest District (Poland, Kostrza Forestry, section 22a), and consists modernized road (in 2019) with open roadside ditches. The formation of natural landslides of the originally very steep slope and deformation of the ditch grade line, including a landslide of the slope, was found. The observed internal friction angles in the soils of the landslide slope are very close to the average values in similar soils. The soil slid into the ditch and raised its bottom by more than 0.60 meters in places, resulting in the loss of patency of the ditch and severely limiting the functioning of this element of road drainage. However, part of the slope remained in its original, very high gradients and did not change its geometry.

KEY WORDS

close-range photogrammetry, escarpment plane stability, excavation escarpment, landslide, low altitude drone flight

Introduction

The durability of structures is a fundamental requirement of their use in engineering activities. Functionality is also linked to the safety of the users as well as the structure itself and the costs incurred for maintenance and repair in their life cycle. In forest road engineering, the basic structures are the road body (or road track), bridges, culverts, and drainage systems (surface and subsurface). The performance of the entire road network largely depends on the durability and efficiency of these elements, which translates directly into the effectiveness of economic activities and the effectiveness of fire protection of forest stands (Ustawa, 1991; Gołąb *et al.*, 2006; Gołąb, 2011; Czerniak *et al.*, 2013).

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Roadside ditches are designed to carry away water from surface runoff, but also to remove from the road body by the drainage layer (Miler, 2013). The effectiveness of the ditches is determined by the durability of the geometry of the bed and the cross-section (Croke *et al.*, 2001). The ditch bottom in areas of reduced longitudinal slope is silted up with the fine soil fractions that water transports from locations higher up and with steeper gradients. In turn, erosion cavities are created in the bottom and bases of the escarpments at these locations with higher longitudinal gradients (Miler, 2013). The stability of escarpment planes depends mainly on the type of soil, its moisture content and the scarp slope, but also anti-erosion protection in the form of turfing or technical development. Under forest conditions, anti-erosion protection is rarely performed, and the escarpment slope is often too high, resulting in localised landslides, blocking the flow of water in the ditches and severely weakening the basic function of this drainage element (Miler, 2013). This affects the increased moisture content of the soil in the body, which reduces the load-bearing capacity of the pavement construction layers and limits the forestry management capabilities (Zarski, 1986).

Variable contactless monitoring methods can be used to scan the forest road surface. An example is the application of mobile laser profilometry on the various categories of forest roads (Ferenčík *et al.*, 2019), independent of weather conditions (except for snow and ice directly on the road) and processing of the data in the office. Another example is the close-range photogrammetry (CRP) technique, based on digital photogrammetry workflows, including image matching, bundle block adjustment or structure from motion (SfM) techniques. Compared with classic digital photogrammetry, where step-by-step solution including interior, relative and absolute orientation is processed, the SfM techniques offer a more automatized workflow, which is easier for users (Fonstad *et al.*, 2013). It allows us to generate three-dimensional (3D) models using overlapping images acquired from different perspectives with standard compact cameras and geo-referencing information. Ferenčík *et al.* (2022) used CRP SfM inside a forest stand to detect soil damage by wheeled skidders. Rieke-Zapp and Nearing's (2005) soil erosion measurements experiment shows that CRP may provide even a 1 mm accuracy level. Borowski *et al.* (2017) used the CRP SfM, supported by invar dimension control marks, to highly accurate (~0.24 mm) inventory of temporary construction objects. For larger areas, *e.g.* detailed reconstruction of road surface morphology and deformation detection, aerial photogrammetry may be used, whether a camera is mounted on an aeroplane (Hejmanowska and Warchoń, 2010) or on unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) (Apollo *et al.*, 2023; Guan *et al.*, 2023; Sifali and Tsioras, 2024). The advantage of photogrammetry is the low cost of equipment, whereas the disadvantage is the barriers that limit the collection of ground observations *e.g.* under dense forest canopy. In such situations, the aerial LiDAR benefits, as the method provides more data and its better accuracy *e.g.* for road surface inventory (Kardoš *et al.*, 2024). For all these reasons, it was assumed that experiment data collection (ditch inventory) would occur under the canopy of the trees by low-altitude (<5 m) UAV flight, by SfM technique, with a level of accuracy of about 5 mm.

In addition, the quality and durability of the slopes of the escarpment that contribute to forest road tracks are determined using a suitable *in situ* test. In particular, soil compaction is to be determined, which, on the one hand, influences the maintenance of slope stability from a geotechnical point of view (Gupta *et al.*, 2016) and, on the other hand, soil penetrability by the root system of trees (Baver *et al.*, 1972). Among the available types of field tests, it was necessary to choose a method that would produce reproducible results, independent of the instrument operator, with proper cost-efficiency (Herrick and Jones, 2002), and at the same time have high mobility, allowing free operation in forest terrain. A test with such advantages is the DCP dynamic penetrometric

test, considered one of the most comprehensive test methods (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2008). In addition to strength parameters, it allows an excellent estimation of soil compaction based on the number of impacts and penetration depth using the correct interpretive formula. The DCP test must be supplemented by soil reconnaissance at least by macroscopic analysis, and for more accurate determinations also by laboratory tests. The testing program can be expanded to very advanced tests, such as triaxial compression testing (Lipiński and Wdowska, 2010). It is then necessary to have samples with intact structure (Carr *et al.*, 2020), which is often problematic, and is avoided in the case of reconstructed samples prepared according to a strict procedure (Lal *et al.*, 2023). Efficiency comparison of mixture formulations in the stabilization/solidification of the loess silt contaminated with zinc in terms of mechanical properties (Lal *et al.*, 2023), obtaining a homogeneous and reproducible test sample. The scope of the research envisaged in the present work included the determination of complete physical properties of soils, hence it was necessary to take samples with intact structure.

The subject of the work is the durability of the geometry of the slope of the ditch, which drains the forest operational trail (Fig. 1). The aim of the work is to observe the stability of the slope plane of a roadside ditch using photogrammetry.

Materials and methods

The data sample – the analysed section of the trail – was modernized in 2018 and is part of the communication network of the Limanowa Forest District (Poland, Kostrza Forestry, section 22a). The modernization consisted of strengthening the structure of the ground surface profiled with a separation layer between the substrate and the substructure in the form of a geosynthetic fabric, using wooden elements in the substructure layer (debarked, impregnated fir rolls) and laying and mechanically stabilizing the gravel roadway layer. Surface drainage, due to the small longitudinal slope of the roadway, was implemented in the form of an open ditch, but its external escarpment was formed at a large inclination (from approx. 92% to approx. 148%).

Fig. 1.

The escarpment of the ditch at the period of observation 2019-2021, own study

The average slopes of the road system at this location were as follows: road (longitudinal slope): 1.6-2.7%; road (cross slope): 0.3-3.5%; ditch by the road (longitudinal slope): 7.0%; skidding track (longitudinal slope): 8.5-16.2%; ditch by the skidding track (longitudinal slope): 14.2%.

The slope located directly above the observed escarpment is characterized by a decline of approx. 45% and lies at an altitude of approx. 380 m above sea level (<https://www.geoportal.gov.pl>). It is covered with forest with the following species composition: main stand: 5 *Abies*, 2 *Fagus*, 1 *Quercus* (aged 79 years), 1 *Abies* (109 years) and 1 *Abies* (64 years), in places *Fagus* (64 and 109 years), *Picea* (79 years) and *Sorbus*. (64 years). In the undergrowth 10 *Abies* (29 years), in the understory *Corylus* and *Sorbus*. The main stand reaches the I and II bonitation class with dimensions: breast height from 29 to 47 cm, height from 23 to 29 m. The stand grows on the Mixed Upland Forest habitat, fresh variant, soil type: brown podzolized. Late thinnings are planned for the stand. The forest serves as a soil and water protector (<https://www.bdl.lasy.gov.pl/portal/mapy>).

Close-range photogrammetric (CRP) observations collected in 2019, 2020 and 2021 and soil samples (collected in 2022) were used for the analyses. The first UAV flight was carried out shortly after the completion of the road modernisation, with subsequent flights repeated in the following years in early spring.

The photogrammetric flights were made in early spring, before the start of vegetation, due to the later development of annual vegetation on the escarpments and at the edges of the road. Three flights were made for comparison in the years: 2019 (just after the completion of construction works), 2020 and 2021, using a DJI Mavic Pro drone. The following flight parameters were used: manual control, flight below tree crowns 3-5 m above ground level (AGL), flight speed approx. 0.5 m s⁻¹, percentage of photo overlap approx. 70% along and approx. 70% in across the examined section, recording a FHD 24 fps movie (photo separation approximately every 20th frame). The collected material was processed in the Agisoft PhotoScan Professional ver. 1.4.3 obtaining digital terrain models (LCM) and orthomosaics.

The data collected was calibrated against five reference points, established in 2019. These points were elements of a traverse, in the local coordinate and elevation system, established for a larger site than the one analysed, therefore their location cannot be included in the drawings, although one of them was located approx. 1 m from the upper edge of the ditch on the natural slope. All points of the reference system were located in places not exposed to shifting and were not checked for the stability of coordinates in the following years. Surveying measurements were taken using an optical total station.

The LCM's rasters were aligned in terms of pixel size to 2 mm (SAGA GIS 2.3.2) and cropped to the area of the selected escarpment (QGIS 3.14.0). Raster differences were then made by subtracting from the current raster the one made in the previous year: 2021-2020 and 2020-2019. Subsequently, based on the analysis of the 2019 LCM and the difference rasters, a section of the slope 15 metres long was selected and the line of the ditch bottom and 16 lines of cross-sections (every 1 m) were drawn on it to observe the stability of the slope (Fig. 2). Using the obtained LCMs and the cross-section lines and the ditch bottom line, cross-sections of the slope and a vertical cross-section along the ditch bottom line were made (QGIS 3.22.3, plug-in 'Profile tool'). The numerical data of these cross-sections were visualised in the form of corresponding graphs. In the graphs presented, an attempt has been made to align the units on the vertical and horizontal axes for ease of comparison, but this is merely an exercise in 'stretching the graph area'. Based on the cross-sections, the places of penetrometric tests were indicated (Fig. 2) and the place of collecting undisturbed soil samples for laboratory tests of basic physical and mechanical properties. Soil samples were collected in measuring cylinders ($f=50\text{ m}^{-3}$, $h=50\text{ m}^{-3}$) and the following were determined on their basis (PN-86/B-02480, 1986; PN-ISO 11465, 1999; Myślińska, 2016):

Fig. 2.

Diagram of the location of cross sections and ground test sites, own study

- current humidity (moisture content) – dryer-weighing method,
- granulation by: sieve method (for fraction = 1 m^{-3}) and laser diffraction (for $<1 \text{ m}^{-3}$),
- ground bulk density,
- organic matter content by high temperature roasting method,
- Hazen's filtration coefficient based on ground grain size.

Soil testing were carried out using an dynamic penetrometer (ASAE Standards, 1998; Herrick and Jones, 2002) with a cone base $\phi 20 \text{ m}^{-3}$, a weight of 2 kg and 0.317 m of height. Measurements were carried out until soil penetration of 0.50 m was achieved.

Results

The drainage ditch area's digital terrain model (DTM) was obtained in 2019, 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 3). 2019's flight did not include the top edge of the slope. These 3 models were then used to calculate the raster's height differences (Fig. 4), obtain the ditch bottom grade lines (Fig. 5) and cross sections (Fig. 6).

The differential raster in 2020 (one year after the road modernisation) (Fig. 4c), apart from the stability of the roadway zone, shows an increase the elevation of the ditch bottom within the limits of 0.10-0.23 m and also a slight increase in elevation of the slope plane, with the exception of a relatively small area near the central part of the slope, where a negative change of 0.10-0.15 m was already visible. The differential raster 2021-2019 (Fig. 4b) shows soil displacement from the central part of the scarp, where large negative changes are visible, to the ditch, where in turn large increases in soil mass are observed. The third (2021-2020) raster (Fig. 4a), compared with the raster after the first year (Fig. 4c), indicates that in the plane of the slope a large erosional

Fig. 3.

Digital terrain models for the observed escarpment in 2019-2021, own study

Fig. 4.

Differential raster with histograms 2019-2021, own study

Fig. 5.

The grade line of the bottom of the ditch observed in the years: 2019, 2020 and 2021, own study

change occurred only in the second year, after a one-year period of relative stability. Each raster shows a few large surface uplift (up to about 0.80-0.90 m), which should be interpreted as obscuring the ground by the developing vegetation.

After one and two years of road modernisation, the grade lines of the ditch bottom (Fig. 5) show a relatively uniform elevation uplift and then soil deposition from the landslide slope. The elevation of the grade line observed in the first year (yellow line) can be associated to some extent with the washing out of soil particles from the slope. However, highly probable, that a large amount of soil washed out from the parts of the ditch and the surface of the skidding trail located above the observed area was deposited in this place. At the observation site, the ditch bottom slope is small and the lifting force decreased significantly here, resulting in the mentioned deposition. After two years (red line), much greater changes in the grade line resulted from the slope subsidence. This caused a serious obstruction of water drainage along the ditch and a strong limitation of the ditch function. In such a situation, maintenance works will be necessary (removing the landslide and reconstructing the grade line).

The cross sections of the studied scarp also show the changes in the inclination of its plane (Table 1). In the first year of observation (yellow lines), the slope does not yet tend to change inclination and is stable. In the second year of observation (red lines), the scarp slumped in a large part of the study area, but some fragments preserved the initial slope. This indicates a mosaic of soil and water conditions within the observed area. The very high slopes realised during construction (even above 55° in places) are noteworthy. After the slope landslide, the slopes were formed in a state close to natural, although some of them (even very large ones) remained almost unchanged. The calculated slope change factor, especially in the middle part of the scarp, indicates that slopes formed in this soil will be stable at about twice the slope. The attached magnitudes of the elevation of the ditch bottom level ranges from 0.16-0.62 m and shows the severity of the ditch obstruction problem.

Fig. 6.

Cross sections numbered 1-8 in the years of observation, own study

Fig. 7.

Cross sections numbered 9-16 in the years of observation, own study

Table 1.

Changes in the geometry of the escarpment

Cross section	i_{2019} average slope of the escarpment year 2019	i_{2021} average slope of the escarpment year 2021	$c_i = \frac{i_{2021}}{i_{2019}}$ change factor	$\Delta H_{2021-2019}$ [m] grade line of the bottom of the ditch
1	1.40 : 1 (54°23')	1.12 : 1 (48°19')	0.804	+0.244
2	1.38 : 1 (54°09')	1.16 : 1 (49°16')	0.839	+0.165
3	1.40 : 1 (54°32')	1.44 : 1 (55°11')	1.024	+0.193
4	1.35 : 1 (53°33')	1.40 : 1 (54°28')	1.034	+0.208
5	1.48 : 1 (55°53')	1 : 0.78 (38°01')	0.530	+0.455
6	1.48 : 1 (55°56')	1 : 0.64 (32°31')	0.431	+0.425
7	1.38 : 1 (54°06')	1 : 0.67 (33°38')	0.481	+0.456
8	1.45 : 1 (55°28')	1.23 : 1 (50°57')	0.848	+0.404
9	1.35 : 1 (53°33')	1.23 : 1 (50°56')	0.910	+0.249
10	1.31 : 1 (52°32')	1 : 0.70 (34°49')	0.533	+0.367
11	1.26 : 1 (51°37')	1 : 0.60 (31°02')	0.477	+0.506
12	1.19 : 1 (49°59')	1 : 0.49 (25°56')	0.408	+0.618
13	1.09 : 1 (47°23')	1 : 0.58 (30°07')	0.534	+0.459
14	1.06 : 1 (46°41')	1.01 : 1 (45°16')	0.952	+0.221
15	1 : 0.93 (43°01')	1 : 0.91 (42°12')	0.972	+0.160
16	1 : 0.92 (42°40')	1 : 0.82 (39°12')	0.885	+0.176

Fig. 8.

Compactness of ground at selected measurement points (1, 6, 11 and 16) in terms of average values for 0.05 m thick ground layers, own study

The soils taken from the slope and the bottom of the ditch (after it slumped) are similar in terms of granulometric composition, filtration coefficient determined by the grain size curve and other characteristics (Table 2). Their characteristics affect the stability of the formed slopes – and so, according to the literature (Pazdro and Kozerski, 1990; Jeromłowicz, 2014; Myślińska, 2016; Łukasik, 2018; Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2021), the angle of natural slope for the soils found here varies

Table 2.

Characteristics of soil of the tested escarpment

Sample no.	Type of ground*	Fraction content Gr / Sa / Si / Cl [%]	Current humidity [%]	Volume density [Mg·m ⁻³]	Filtration coefficient** [m·s ⁻¹]	Content of organic parts [%]
A1	siSa <i>piasek gliniasty</i>	13 / 66 / 17 / 4	15.3	1.60	2.61E ⁻⁸	0.86
A2	siSa <i>piasek gliniasty</i>	10 / 58 / 26 / 6	34.8	1.13	1.96E ⁻⁸	3.17
A3	siSa <i>pył piaszczysty</i>	9 / 56 / 29 / 6	35.6	1.36	1.67E ⁻⁸	3.18
A4	siSa <i>pył piaszczysty</i>	16 / 50 / 28 / 6	25.1	1.64	1.67E ⁻⁸	1.03
B1	siSa <i>piasek gliniasty</i>	7 / 63 / 24 / 6	29.8	1.36	1.96E ⁻⁸	0.92
B2	grSa <i>piasek gliniasty</i>	32 / 55 / 10 / 3	27.8	1.62	3.76E ⁻⁸	0.87
B3	grsiSa <i>głina</i>	25 / 38 / 26 / 11	38.0	1.46	9.40E ⁻⁹	1.55
B4	siSa <i>piasek gliniasty</i>	20 / 64 / 12 / 4	38.2	1.47	2.27E ⁻⁸	1.28

* according to the standard: PN-EN ISO 14688; according to the old standard: PN-86/B-02480

** according to Hazen $k_{10}=0,0116 \cdot (d_{10})^2$

between 30-40°, while the filtration coefficient indicates very poorly permeable soils. The results of pancentromeric tests performed in the cross-sections on the natural slope next to the upper edge of the scarp are presented in Figure 8. For better readability, the graphs present the average values of soil compactness for layers with a thickness of 0.05 m. Statistical analysis indicates the correctness and advisability of such a solution.

The soil compactness in the profile depth surveyed is not high – it is natural soil, not subjected to additional loads. The values of compactness observed here are many times smaller than those observed in the ruts of the skid trails using the same measurement method (Kormanek and Gołąb, 2021). The compactness plots presented in Figure 8 do not indicate that this soil feature contributed specifically to the slope slump in cross-sections 6 and 11 and its stability in cross-sections 1 and 16. However, the execution of the scarp with a very high slope ratio changed its existing equilibrium conditions by unilaterally removing the support and formed an uncovered plane susceptible to erosion.

In the research presented here, DSM rasters are the main source of landform information. They were developed based on a flight by an unmanned aerial vehicle (close-range photogrammetry below the tree canopy) and repeated for three consecutive years based on the same network of reference points. Vertical and oblique photographs were taken. The pixel size of the obtained rasters varies between 2.4 and 8.6 mm, which makes it possible to draw detailed vertical cross-sections in selected locations and directions and to perform calculations of the magnitude of erosion changes. Differential rasters have been calculated for annual periods and the entire observation period to show the resulting landform changes. The calculations involve subtracting elevation (H) for pixels with the same position coordinates (X and Y). The differential raster can be analysed in arbitrary straight and broken lines. Therefore the ditch grade line and 16 cross sections were chosen.

After the first year of observation, the cross-sections of the escarpment did not show any major changes, while the elevations of the ditch bottom grade line rose by about 0.10-0.20 m (Fig. 6 and 7). The observed elevation of the grade line is the effect of sedimentation of fine material washed down from the higher section of the ditch (also the terrain) with greater longitudinal gradients. In the second year of observation, the escarpment lost stability in the central part of the observed fragment (cross-sections 5-13, Fig. 6 and 7), and the subsiding ground blocked the ditch and significantly limited its drainage function for the road body.

As a result of the landslide, the escarpment grade in sections 5-13 decreased by more than twofold (section 12, Fig. 7, Table 2), and the elevations of the ditch bottom gradeline increased in the extreme case (section 12) by 0.618 m. The smallest difference, 0.16 m, was observed in cross-section 15 (differences between 2021 and 2019).

Discussion

One of the most important parameters of surface road drainage systems is the rate of water drainage from the roadway area. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the solutions used, as emphasized by Weaver *et al.* (2015). Blocking (impeding) water flow in a drainage ditch through soil deposition, as occurred in the study area, significantly slows down the drainage of the road body, worsening traffic conditions. The process of eroding the ditch bottom and undercutting the base of its slopes also has a destructive effect on the road body and adjacent ditch slopes. This leads to costly maintenance and repair work to ensure the durability and functionality of the described infrastructure elements (Czerniak *et al.*, 2013; Weaver *et al.*, 2015). Lipiec and Hatano (2003), Solgi *et al.* (2017), and Grigorev *et al.* (2020), among others, highlight the conditions of slope stability, emphasizing the intensity of economic activities on the road. Surface runoff occurring on surfaces unprotected by vegetation easily washes away fine soil particles, transporting them, and sedimenting them into adjacent areas. This effect was observed in the presented study as early as the first year. The need for rapid erosion protection of bare slopes is emphasized by many authors, including Weaver *et al.* (2015).

These authors, including Czerniak *et al.* (2013), emphasize the need for systematic monitoring of the extent of erosion damage, recommend identifying the circumstances and causes of its occurrence, and suggest removing sediment and vegetation only when necessary. If more serious problems occur, it is recommended (Weaver *et al.*, 2015) to reduce slope gradients, sod the surface, and widen the ditch to ensure water flow.

Specific conditions that exacerbate slope erosion include slope inclination, soil type, and current soil moisture content. These factors largely determine slope stability, which can be described by the angle of internal friction.

According to the literature (Dzidowska and Noga, 2007; Zydroń and Zgoda, 2012; Zydroń and Borusiński, 2013; Zydroń and Gadowska, 2013; Zawisza and Kula, 2016), the angle of internal friction for clayey soils in a moist state, which determines the limit value of the slope above which the slope is not stable and is exposed to landslides, is 35-40°. The slopes decreased naturally to similar values (Table 2), in several cases slightly larger, but it should be noted that a large amount of soil that had settled to the bottom of the ditch and the counterscarp of the ditch inhibited further movement of the landslide that had formed. Without this support effect, the escarpment would have become stable at even smaller slopes. The data obtained are consistent with the values given in the literature.

The size and dynamics of landslides provide important information related to both economics and safety. Technological advances now enable, in addition to traditional geodetic methods, the

use of laser scanning and satellite, aerial, and UAV (unmanned aerial vehicle) photogrammetry. Karwacki (2019) presented UAV photogrammetric measurements of an active landslide (approximately 1.5 ha) in the Western Carpathians. The author noted the great usefulness of UAV photogrammetric material in observing small objects and the quality of the obtained results. He used flights at altitudes of 52-81 m (AGL), obtaining DTMs with pixel sizes of 1.7-2.1 cm. However, he notes the limitations he encountered in his research related to the cover of the terrain by tall vegetation. In the UAV flights presented in this article, the flights took place at an altitude of approximately 5 m (AGL) to eliminate these circumstances, while obtaining DTMs with smaller pixel sizes. Karwacki (2019), based on his measurements observing large objects transported within the landslide area (large stones or tree fragments), determined numerous displacement vectors for these objects, illustrating the movements of the sliding ground. The slope measurements presented in this article only show its states, without determining the specific displacement of the soil masses. This is due to the size of the observed area and the lack of identifiable objects.

Conclusions

- ✦ Forming external ditch and embankment escarpments with excessively large gradients, which is justified by the desire to reduce the width of the road lane and thus minimize losses of production area, in most cases does not bring the expected effects – nature corrects them itself, limiting some functions of road structures or damaging these structures. As a result, emergency maintenance works and expensive repair works are then necessary.
- ✦ Formed escarpments should be made in the gradients specified in the literature on the subject, even with experience and observation of the escarpments remaining in a stable condition even when the gradients are significantly exceeded.
- ✦ The stability of escarpment is determined by various factors: soil, water, vegetation covering the slope surface and the hillside above, the development state of root systems in this vegetation, the presence of coarser soil skeleton fractions, the orientation of soil profile layers relative to the slope plane, the presence of internal drainage channels and slip planes, the intensity of economic activities on the slope and road, and vibrations from machinery.
- ✦ The observation and measurement technique used here allows for ‘backward observations’ of objects and processes that were not planned to be studied before. In the presented material, the deformations of the road surface and the manoeuvring area during normal operation were initially studied – only after the landslide occurred on the escarpment, the previously recorded photogrammetric material was used to describe changes in the slope condition.
- ✦ Photogrammetric techniques for acquiring knowledge about terrain and the dynamics of its changes are currently widely used in many fields of the economy by engineers, naturalists, hydrologists, the open-pit mining industry, land development designers, managers of land and buildings, and many other fields. This technique is accessible to everyone due to the low costs of data acquisition and the ease of processing and use. The collected data can be very detailed.

Authors' contributions

J.G. – conceived and designed the experiments, performed the experiments; J.G., Ł.B. – analysed the data, wrote the paper, provided the resources, read and improved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors state no conflict of interest.

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Data availability

The raw data can be obtained on request from the corresponding author.

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Zastosowanie fotogrametrii w ocenie stateczności skarpy rowu odwadniającego drogę leśną

Stabilność skarp i niwelety dna rowów, jako elementów torowiska drogowego, jest istotnym czynnikiem utrzymywania w sprawności systemu odwodnienia drogi. W pracy przedstawiono 3-letnie (2019-2021) obserwacje zmian ukształtowania tych elementów przy użyciu fotogrametrii niskiego pułapu. Loty bezzałogowym statkiem powietrznym wykonano w Nadleśnictwie Limanowa na drodze leśnej, którą oddano do użytku po modernizacji nawierzchni i wykonaniu systemu odwodnienia powierzchniowego w postaci otwartych rowów przydrożnych. Praca jest częścią większego opracowania dotyczącego stabilności nawierzchni składnicy drewna w czasie jej eksploatacji oraz pola manewrowego dla pojazdów zrywkowych i wywozowych znajdujących się w bezpośrednim sąsiedztwie badanej skarpy. Po stwierdzeniu w kolejnych nalotach (latach) (ryc. 1) powstania naturalnych osunięć pierwotnie bardzo stromej skarpy i deformacji niwelety dna rowu wygenerowano z posiadanego materiału (NMPT) (ryc. 3) rastry różnicowe (ryc. 4) i wyznaczono linie przekrojów poprzecznych skarpy oraz niweletę rowu (ryc. 2). Jako cel przyjęto obserwację stabilności skarpy rowu przy użyciu fotogrametrii. W opracowaniu przedstawiono wielkości zmian rzędnych gruntu w całym obszarze badań (rastry różnicowe) (ryc. 4) oraz szczegóły tych zmian w wyznaczonych liniach przekrojowych (ryc. 5-7). Wielkość piksela poszczególnych rastrów ($2,4-8,6 \text{ m}^{-3}$) pozwoliła na określenie wielkości zaistniałych zmian z dość dużą szczegółowością i dokładnością. Po pierwszym roku obserwacji niweleta dna rowu została podniesiona o około 0,20 m (tab. 1), co jest wynikiem naniesienia drobnego materiału gruntowego wymytego z terenu położonego wyżej, natomiast skarpy rowu pozostały stabilne i nie uległy deformacji. Po kolejnym roku nastąpiło osunięcie się obserwowanej skarpy z naturalnym uformowaniem spadków około dwukrotnie mniejszych. Cytowane porównawcze dane literaturowe (kąty tarcia wewnętrznego gruntów) są bardzo podobne do tych, które w skarpie uformowały się samoczynnie. Osunięty do rowu grunt (podstawowe właściwości gruntu: tab. 2; wyniki badań penetrometrycznych: ryc. 8) podniósł niweletę jego dna miejscami o ponad 0,60 m, co spowodowało utratę drożności rowu i poważnie ograniczyło funkcjonowanie tego elementu odwodnienia drogi. W takiej sytuacji konieczne są interwencyjne prace utrzymaniowe przywracające możliwość odpływu wody rowem. Część skarpy pozostała jednak w pierwotnie ukształtowanych, bardzo dużych spadkach i nie zmieniła swojej geometrii. Nie oznacza to jednak przyzwolenia dla praktyki wykonywania skarp o znacznie przekroczonych wielkościach spadków, co uzasadniane jest dążeniem do wyłączenia z produkcji leśnej jak najmniejszej powierzchni. Sama metoda oraz sprzęt użyty do określania zmian geometrii płaszczyzn torowiska drogowego poddanych działaniu różnych sił (gravitacja, manewry sprzętu zrywkowego, ruch ciężkich pojazdów wywozowych, wibracje) daje ciekawe rezultaty, o niespotykanej wcześniej rozdzielczości i dokładności.